

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF "TOM SAWYER" BY MARK TWAIN AND "SHUM BOLA" BY GAFUR GULOM

Abdumalikova Saidabonu

Angren university, 2nd stage student.

saidabonuabdumalikova@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10468775>

Abstract. This scientific article aims to explore the thematic and stylistic similarities and differences between two iconic literary works from distinct cultural backgrounds: "The Adventures of Tom Sawyer" by Mark Twain and "Shum bola" by Gafur Gulom. Through an examination of the narrative frameworks, character lines, and socio-cultural backgrounds of these books, we hope to shed light on the range of viewpoints that these well-known writers offer.

Key words: Artistic comparative analysis, adventure, naughtiness, independence, orphans, friends, autobiographical elements, stylistic originality.

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ «ТОМА СОЙЕРА» МАРКА ТВЕЙНА И «ШУМ БОЛА» ГАФУРА ГУЛОМА

Аннотация. Целью данной научной статьи является исследование тематических и стилистических сходств и различий между двумя знаковыми литературными произведениями разных культур: «Приключения Тома Сойера» Марка Твена и «Шум бола» Гафура Гулома. Путем изучения повествовательных рамок, линий персонажей и социокультурного происхождения этих книг мы надеемся пролить свет на диапазон точек зрения, которые предлагают эти известные писатели.

Ключевые слова: Художественный сравнительный анализ, приключение, озорство, самостоятельность, сироты, друзья, автобиографические элементы, стилистическое своеобразие.

Well-known works like "Tom Sawyer" and "Shum Bola" came from different cultural contexts. Twain's American classic, which takes place in the Midwest in the 19th century, presents a nostalgic picture of childhood experiences. In the meantime, "Shum bola", Gulom's Uzbek book, explores the complexities of Central Asian society norms and identity. The common topic of coming-of-age and self-discovery is explored in both stories, despite their geographical difference.

Looking at the details, although great writers Mark Twain and Gafur Gulom did not live at the same time, their masterpieces have many similarities according to their genre. Both narratives provide the adventure of protagonists named Tom Sawyer in "The adventures of Tom Sawyer" and Koravoy in "Shum Bola". For this reason, we are able to know that the genre of both books is adventure. Adventure was originally a Middle English word derived from the Old French adventure meaning "destiny," "fate," or "chance event." Today, we define adventure as a remarkable or unexpected journey, experience, or event that a person participates in because of chance. This last detail, a result of chance, is a key element of adventure; the stories usually involve a character who is brought to the adventure by chance, and chance usually plays a large role in the

episodes of the story. Also, adventures usually include dangerous situations, narrow escapes, problems to be solved through intelligence and skill, exotic people and places, and brave deeds.¹

	<i>Books</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Published year</i>	<i>Protagonists</i>	<i>Genre</i>	<i>Main idea</i>
1.	“The adventures of Tom Sawyer”	Mark Twain	1876	Tom Sawyer	Adventure	Adventure, exploration, and discovery are central themes in the American experience. It is at the core of The Adventures of Tom Sawyer. Tom is an adventurer, an explorer, and a thrill-seeker, driven by his imagination and sense of nobility. ²
2.	“Shum bola”	Gafur Gulom	1936	Koravoy	Adventure	the tale of a fourteen-year-old Uzbek boy from Tashkent, who because of his lies and mischievousness, gets himself into a series of amusing scrapes. ³

Table 1st. General information about “The adventures of Tom Sawyer” and “Shum bola”

We can see in the table that the Uzbek author Gafur Gulom is reported to have crafted his masterwork in 1936 based on the sources. However, he initially referred to the work by a different name. Later, after revising the description and a few scenes, the name was also altered. The narrative illustrates the author's early years as well as the perception of Tashkent in the early 1900s.

The book cannot be regarded as autobiographical even though many of the central events are drawn from the writer's life (for instance, the writer acknowledged that he just selected his father's unique looks and remarks for the hero Hoji Bobo). The fantasy and creative texture in it outweigh the accurate historical details. "In essence, this work, with deep national spirit, is close to Mark Twain's "The Adventures of Tom Sawyer" and some of Dicken's novels," said L.Bat about it.

In turn, real people serve as the source of inspiration for numerous characters in Mark Twain's 1876 novel "The Adventures of Tom Sawyer." He portrayed his brother Henry as Cousin Sid and Cousin Mary, his mother as Aunt Polly, and his sister Pamela. His educational experiences are included in the book, and the story's trial scene is set in his father's courtroom. Being a well-known humorist, Mark Twain distinguished himself from many other novels of his era by keeping

¹ Adventure: Definitions and examples LiteraryTerms.net

² Tom Sawyer Themes: What’s All about? NoSweatShakespeare.com

³ Gafur Gulom: Shum bola – The modern novel ThemodernNovelBlog.com

to American topics, places, and language. These characteristics had a significant influence on several authors who came after him.

The authors of the mentioned works produced realistic images of orphan youngsters. The way the visuals are written demonstrates both writers' abilities. Tom lives in Polly's aunt's house with his younger brother and sister. In addition, Koravoy lives with his single mother and has a younger brother and sister. The heroes of the novels are shown to be youthful, social, naughty children who don't feel any duty to anyone other than their family at the beginning. Boys who would rather play in the streets than learn in class. The paragraphs that follow demonstrate that Tom and Koravoy play with their friends on the street for the entirety of the day:

*Tom did play hokey, and he had a very good time. He got back home barely in season to help Jim, the small colored boy, saw next-day's wood and split the kindling before supper — at least he was there in time to tell his adventures to Jim while Jim did three fourths of the work.*⁴

*Ertadan kechgacha ko`cha changitib hammaning joniga tegib, kampirlardan qarg`ish eshitib, o`spirinlardan kaltak yeb, sandiroqlab yuradigan o`vin-to`da bekorchi bolalarmiz.*⁵

Despite both protagonists are naughty and irresponsible, they can make friends easily and spend a great time with their friends. In some cases, we can also see that Tom and Koravoy have loyalty and care for their friends. It is also worth mentioning that Tom's best friends are Huckleberry Finn and Joe Harper while the name of Koravoy's friend is Omon.

The analysis of the works by Mark Twain and Gafur Gulom clearly indicate that their writing style are very similar to each other with describing people and characters, setting and events, social issues and problems.

By analyzing these rare works, we can come to the following conclusions: As it is evident from the examples, "The adventures of Tom Sawyer" and "Shum Bola" have a number of similar features in setting, character description, plot development and so on. American novelist Mark Twain and Uzbek writer Gafur Gulom are outstanding representatives of realism, who could create a vivid picture of social life of their time by exposing the bitter truth of it in a sharp humoristic way. For their work they equally used their own experiences. Both writers used the life and adventures of orphan children as a tool for revealing the darkness of society.

REFERENCES

1. Abdurahimova Charos Anvar qizi, "THE ANALYSIS OF CHARACTERS IN "THE ADVENTURES OF TOM SAWYER" BY MARK TWAIN", Vol.1 No.3 2022
2. Shuqin Li, "A Probe into the Profile of Tom Sawyer in The Adventures of Tom Sawyer", June 3, 2013
3. Navro'zova Gulrux, "G'AFUR G'ULOMNING "SHUM BOLA" ASARIDA OBRAZLARNING PSIXOLOGIK TALQINI", June 18, 2023
4. Saminova Mashxuraxon Rafiqjon qizi, Ziyoxidinova Kamola Mahammadjon qizi, "MARK TVEN VA GOFUR GULOM QISSALARINING QIYOSIY-LISONIY TAHLILI", 2023

⁴ "The adventures of Tom Sawyer", Mark Twain

⁵ "Shum bola", Gafur Gulom

5. Zilola Tolibovna Safarova, Darmon Saidakhmedovna Urayeva, “THE SIMILAR FEATURES IN DEPICTION OF ORPHANS’ LIFE IN CHILDREN’S ADVENTURE NOVELS”, April 18, 2020